

COURSE OF ACUTE OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article provides information about the study of a retrospective analysis of 307 case histories of children aged 3 months to 3 years with the main diagnosis of acute obstructive bronchitis. The aim of our work was to determine the features of the course of acute obstructive bronchitis in young children and to establish the possibility of using integral hematological parameters to assess the severity of intoxication and predict the course of the disease.

Key words: obstructive bronchitis, young children, course

Relevance. The leading place in the structure of childhood morbidity is occupied by diseases of the respiratory system, which, according to various literature data, account for 50 to 90% of all cases of seeking medical help, depending on the season of the year. In 30% of children, respiratory infections occur with a clinic of obstructive bronchitis, and in 30-50% of cases it takes a protracted, undulating or recurrent course. The main etiological factors of obstructive bronchitis are respiratory viral, chlamydial and mycoplasmal infections. Currently, the incidence of this pathology is steadily increasing, which is associated with an increase in the number of frequently ill children, an increase in the survival rate of premature newborns with severe lesions of the respiratory and other systems, an increase in the number of children with atopy, and the action of a wide range of adverse environmental factors, including passive smoking.

Purpose: To determine the features of the course of acute obstructive bronchitis in young children and to establish the possibility of using integral hematological parameters to assess the severity of intoxication and predict the course of the disease.

Objectives: To study the incidence of acute obstructive bronchitis depending on age, gender, season of the year. To study the influence of certain factors (the course of pregnancy and childbirth, allergic history, GER, otitis, anemia) on the risk of development, severity and duration of acute obstructive bronchitis. To study the etiological structure of acute obstructive bronchitis and the effect of the pathogen on its course. To study the possibility of using integral hematological parameters in clinical practice to assess the severity of acute obstructive bronchitis.

Material and methods. To achieve the goals set, a retrospective analysis of 307 case histories of children aged from 3 months to 3 years with the main diagnosis of acute obstructive bronchitis was carried out. The main materials of the study were the data of obstetric, family, allergic anamnesis, anamnesis of the patient's life. To study the integral hematological parameters, we used the data of the general blood test, in particular, the leukocyte formula, upon admission of children to the hospital and at discharge. Formulas for calculating indices are given in the literature. The obtained data were statistically processed on a personal computer using the STATISTIKA application package.

Results and its discussion. The dynamics of the incidence of acute obstructive bronchitis (hereinafter referred to as AOB) for the year was determined. There were two peaks of AAR, the first one occurred in the autumn months and the second, more pronounced, in January-March, which can be explained by the increase in the significance of acute respiratory viral infection in these periods.

The structure of the incidence of AOD among young children from 3 months to 3 years was as follows: boys were sick significantly more often (60.9%) than girls (39.1%). To assess the age peak among children under 3 years old, 4 groups were distinguished: group 1 - from 3 months to 6 months, group 2 - from 6 months to 1 year, groups 3 and 4 - from 1 year to 2 years and from 2 years to 3 years respectively.

OOB occurred mainly in children of the 2nd (30%), 3rd (28%) and 4th (28%) groups. There were no statistically significant differences by gender in the age structure. Allergic anamnesis was aggravated in 32.3% of all cases of AOB. It should be noted that food allergy (17%) with sensitization to cow's milk, chicken, and eggs was the leading one in the structure. 9% of children had atopic dermatitis, less often drug allergy, allergic conjunctivitis, urticaria, etc., as well as their combination.

When studying the obstetric anamnesis, pathological conditions during pregnancy and childbirth, the time and method of delivery were assessed. No statistically significant factors influencing the possible incidence of AOB have been identified. An important link in the diagnosis and tactics of managing children with bronchitis is the allocation of risk groups for the possible development of bronchial obstruction.

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To solve this problem, the premorbid background of children was studied in order to identify risk factors for the development of AOD, as well as to identify conditions that aggravate its course. Of the comorbidities prevailed: nasopharyngitis in 95%, otitis - 15%, GER - 9.5%, anemia - 7.5% of all cases (n=307). It should be noted that in 11% of cases there was a combination of the above diseases.

To assess the effect of the premorbid background on the duration of AOB, the number of bed-days of hospital stay was estimated. The results were compared with the average hospital stay of children with AOD, which was 7.1 bed-days. There was a tendency to increase the length of stay in the hospital in the presence of concomitant pathologies (GER, otitis media, allergic diseases) and especially in their combination (otitis media - 7, 35 bed-days; combination of otitis media and allergies - 8.7; GER - 9.5; combination of GER and allergy - 11.1; GER, anemia and otitis media - 15.5 bed-days),

The severity of AOB was assessed by determining the degree of respiratory failure in children upon admission to the hospital. Respiratory failure was detected in 83% of cases, and in 57% - DN 0-I degree, 22%

- DN I, 4% - DN I-II degree. Significant was the presence of concomitant pathology in 58% of children with DN I/I-II degree in the form of allergies (19%), a combination of anemia, GER, MARS, etc. (16%), congenital heart disease and MARS (13%), otitis media (6%), GER (4%).

To study the viral etiology of the disease, a smear-imprint from the nasopharynx was taken from the nasopharynx for RIF in 72% of patients, and a positive result was obtained in 28%. The leading etiological infectious agent was the RS virus (59%), less often adenovirus, influenza A and B viruses, and parainfluenza. In 20 patients, the blood was examined for the detection of antibodies to M.pneumonia and Ch.pneumonia, as a result of which Ig class M was detected: to mycoplasma in 23%, to chlamydia - 7% of cases.

RS infection occurred evenly throughout the year. Patients were received on the 3-5th day from the onset of the disease in 100% of cases with respiratory failure syndrome: DN 0-I degree in 80%, DN I and DN I-II in 10%, respectively. It was revealed that in 60% of children the body temperature remained within the normal range, 40% had fever, and the rise in temperature above 38.5o within 4-6 days from the onset of the disease was recorded in 30% of children, the subfebrile temperature of 37.5o was kept at for 3 days in 10% of patients.

The degree of endogenous intoxication (hereinafter - EI) is a criterion for the severity of the general condition of the patient. One of the indicators characterizing the severity of EI are integral hematological parameters. Intoxication indices were taken for the study, namely, the leukocyte index of intoxication according to L. Ya. Kalf-Kalif (hereinafter referred to as LII), LII in the modification of B. A. Reis; an indicator of inflammation activity - an index of the ratio of leukocytes and ESR (hereinafter - ILSOE) and an index of allergization. These hematological parameters were studied in two groups of children with AOB: group 1 - cases of MS infection (n=40), group 2 - patients with concomitant otitis media (n=62). The calculation was carried out on the basis of the data of the general blood test taken upon admission of patients and at discharge, the results obtained are expressed as a percentage.

The analysis of integral hematological indices showed their informativeness in both studied groups. Indexes of intoxication (LII and LII in the modification of B. A. Reis) with a value below the norm indicate more about the viral etiology of the disease. When comparing both groups, it was found that upon admission to the hospital LII and LII in the modification of B.A. children of the 1st group (11.1%), which may indicate the participation of a bacterial pathogen in the etiology of the disease in children of the 2nd group. A higher than normal value also reflects the inflammatory component of the disease, which tends to decrease at the time of release. However, since the moment of clinical recovery, the percentage of children with low levels of LII in both groups has significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased, which may indicate a certain tension in the immune system and, as a result, a possible risk of recurrent respiratory infection.

In both study groups, there was an increase in the allergization index, which may indicate the impact of allergy on the incidence of AOD. High indices of the index were noted upon admission and, to a greater extent, upon discharge of patients from the hospital. The latter can be explained by the possible allergic effect of antibacterial agents used in therapy.

ILSOE makes it possible to judge the activity of inflammation and the presence of intoxication associated with an infectious genesis with a decrease in the indicator below the norm. In most patients, ILSOE was noted below the norm, which by the time of discharge tended to normalize, which confirms the infectious genesis of AOB.

When using integral hematological parameters, the possibility of obtaining comprehensive information about the immunological state of the body is expanded than with the usual assessment of a hemogram. Integral indicators assess the degree and severity of the inflammatory process at the moment, which makes it possible to choose further diagnostic tactics, and most importantly, predict the severity of the current pathological process and the risk of re-infection.

Conclusions: AOD in young children was more common in the age range from 6 months to 1 year, and boys were sick more often (60.9%). The disease is characterized by seasonality with a peak in the autumn months and from January to March.

The risk group for the development of AOB should include children with a burdened allergic history (in particular, with food allergies) and GER, as well as their combination. Aggravating the course of AOB with the phenomenon of respiratory failure syndrome are concomitant diseases - anemia and otitis media, which, along with risk factors, significantly increases the length of stay in the hospital.

The main etiological significance in the development of AOB was made by RS-viral infection (59%), which was recorded mainly in children from 1 to 3 years of age and proceeded with respiratory failure syndrome, prolonged fever.

The use of integral hematological parameters in this work showed the need for further in-depth study of them with a view to their possible application in clinical practice. Their use is aimed at assessing the state of various parts of the immune system in dynamics without the use of special additional studies, as well as for assumptions of the genesis of an infectious disease and assessment of the patient's condition at the initial stage of the disease and against the background of ongoing treatment.

Literature:

1. Davlatovich A. X. et al. PAPULYOZ DERMATOZINI DAVOLASH UCHUN PIMICRALIMUS BILAN MAXALLIY DAVOLASHNI QO'LLASH //IQRO. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 79-82.
2. Ilyaevna P. U. et al. MODERN TRENDS IN TREATMENT SICK MICROSPORIA //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 16. – №. 2. – C. 98-106.
3. Jo‘raqulovich U. A. et al. ADVANTAN FOYDALANISH ALLERGIY VA YALIGLI DERMATOZLARNI TASHQI TERAPIYA //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 16. – №. 2. – C. 56-66.

4. Bahodirovich T. I. et al. DERMATOSCOPIC PAINTING ACUTE AND CHRONIC INFLAMMATORY AND ALLERGIC DERMATOSES //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – T. 31. – №. 3. – C. 63-72.
5. Ilyaevna P. U. et al. DERMATOSCOPIC PAINTING SOME COMMON DERMATOSES //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 16. – №. 2. – C. 107-120.
6. Davlatovich A. S. et al. SKINOREN GEL PAPULYOZI BO ‘LGAN KAMMALARNI KOMPLEKS TERAPIYADA PUSTULAR FORMASI ROSACEA //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 16. – №. 2. – C. 83-90.
7. Abdusalamovich R. I. et al. ROLE OUTDOOR THERAPIES IN COMPLEX TREATMENT SICK WITH VULGAR AND ACNE ROSE //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – T. 31. – №. 3. – C. 73-83.
8. Kholikovich E. S. et al. APPLICATION OF" BETASALIK" OINTMENT IN THE THERAPY OF CHRONIC INFLAMMATORY AND ALLERGIC DERMATOSES //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – T. 31. – №. 3. – C. 56-62.
9. Xolikovich E. S. et al. TAJRIBASI FOYDALANISH PANAVIDA IN DAVOLASH KASAL PAPILOMAVIRUS INFEKTSION ANOGENITAL HUDUDLAR //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 16. – №. 2. – C. 91-97.
10. Jo‘raqulovich U. A. et al. TAJRIBASI FOYDALANISH TERBIZILA IN DAVOLASH MIKROSPORADA BOLALAR VA KATTALAR //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 16. – №. 2. – C. 67-72.
11. Abdusalamovich R. I. et al. AZELAY KISLOTA PAYLASHMALARI-PAPULOZ-PUSTULOZ VA ROSE AKNELARINI DAVOLASH //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 16. – №. 2. – C. 73-79.
12. Jorakulovich U. A. et al. External Therapy of Allergic and Inflammatory Dermatoses Using Advantan. – 2023.

13. Davlatovich A. X. et al. Using Dermatoscopy to Identify and Differentiate Between Acute and Chronic Inflammatory and Allergic Skin Conditions. – 2023.
14. Abdusalamovich R. I. et al. The Significance of Incorporating Outdoor Therapies into a Comprehensive Treatment Plan for Individuals with Common Acne Vulgaris and Rosacea. – 2023.
15. Жалилов А. Х., Ачилова Ф. А. ЖЕЛЕЗОДЕФИЦИТНАЯ АНЕМИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ И ЕЁ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 123-127.
16. Ачилова Ф., Ибатов Ш., Абдукадирова А. ЭХОКАРДИОГРАФИЯ ВОУЇСНА БОЛАЛАРДА КИЧИК YURAK ANOMALIYALARINING TARQALISHI //Международный журнал научной педиатрии. – 2022. – №. 5. – С. 11-15.
17. Жалилов А., Ачилова Ф. Эффективность комплексной терапии железодефицитной анемии у детей //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2016. – №. 3 (89). – С. 25-28.
18. Ачилова Ф. А., Жалилов А. Х. ДАННЫЕ ЭХОКАРДИОГРАФИИ ПРИ МАЛЫХ АНОМАЛИЙ СЕРДЦА У ДЕТЕЙ //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 136-140.
19. Кодирова М., Хайдарова С., Ачилова Ф. КЛИНИКА И ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРИЗНАКИ НЕВРОТИЧЕСКОГО МИОКАРДИТА НА ЭКГ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА //Журнал гепато-гастроэнтерологических исследований. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.1. – С. 30-32.
20. Эрметов А. Т. и др. Случай пункционного метода лечения абсцесса печени при деструктивном аппендиците, осложненном пилефлебитом //Вестник экстренной медицины. – 2013. – №. 2. – С. 72-74.
21. Жалилов А., Ачилова Ф. Эффективность комплексной терапии железодефицитной анемии у детей //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2016. – №. 3 (89). – С. 25-28.

22. Ачилова Ф., Жалилов А. Показатели эхокардиографии при малых аномалиях сердца у детей //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2017. – №. 1 (93). – С. 33-35.
23. Абдурахманова С. Современные подходы к диагностике и лечению сочетанных форм миомы матки и аденомиоза у женщин репродуктивного возраста //in Library. – 2020. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 1-141.
24. Kh J. A., Sh M. U., Achilova F. A. The state of the erythron system in acute pneumonia in children. – 2022.
25. Нажимов Ш. Р. У. и др. Особенности показателей перекисного окисления липидов при хронических гематурических нефритах у детей //Достижения науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 12 (53). – С. 56-58.
26. Пирманова Ш. С. и др. Характеристика остеопении при тубулоинтерстициальных заболеваниях почек у детей //Достижения науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 12 (53). – С. 53-56.
27. Уралов Ш. и др. ABOUT MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF ACUTE STENOSING LARYNGOTRACHEITIS IN CHILDREN //Международный журнал научной педиатрии. – 2022. – №. 5. – С. 25-31.
28. Ахматова Ю. и др. ХРОНИЧЕСКИЙ ТУБУЛОИНТЕРСТИЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НЕФРИТ (ХТИН) У ДЕТЕЙ НА ФОНЕ УРАТУРИИ: КЛИНИКО-ЛАБОРАТОРНАЯ И ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА //InterConf. – 2020.
29. Ахматов А., Ахматова Ю., Сирожова Н. ПИЕЛОНЕФРИТ У ДЕТЕЙ: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ //InterConf. – 2020.
30. Рахмонов З. М. и др. Компенсаторно-приспособительная реакция сосудистого русла внутренних органов при резекции желудка //International Scientific and Practical Conference World science. – ROST, 2017. – Т. 5. – №. 6. – С. 42-44.

31. Хусанов Э. У., Коржавов Ш. О., Сулейманов Р. И. Исследование экскреции лактата кожей в зависимости от различных факторов //Re-health journal. – 2019. – №. 2. – С. 72-75.
32. Oblakulovich K. S. et al. The Thymus gland (Thymus) aspects in children (review of literature) //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 9-16.
33. Хусанов Э. У., Коржавов Ш. О., Ортикбаева Н. Т. Морфологическая картина дегрануляции апудоцитов гастродуоденальной зоны при экспериментальном голодании //International Scientific and Practical Conference World science. – ROST, 2017. – Т. 5. – №. 5. – С. 59-61.
34. Коржавов Ш. О. и др. Развитие микроциркуляторного русла аффлекторов кожи в постнатальном онтогенезе //International Scientific and Practical Conference World science. ROST. – 2017. – Т. 5. – №. 5. – С. 41-43.
35. Негматова Г. Ш. и др. Особенности аутоиммунный тиреоидит в условиях йодного дефицитного региона //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 356-359.
36. Каттаходжаева Д., Муминов О. Морфологическое изменения надпочечников на фоне сахарного диабета : дис. – ТГМУ имени абу Али ибн сино, 2022.
37. Курбонова З. Ч., Бабаджанова Ш. А., Муминов О. А. Лабораторный мониторинг патологии коагуляционного гемостаза у больных COVID-19. – 2021.
38. Курбонова З. Ч. и др. Характеристика функции тромбоцитов при COVID-19. – 2021.
39. Бабаджанова Ш. А., Курбонова З. Ч., Муминов О. А. Частота тромбоэмболических осложнений у больных с коронавирусной инфекцией. – 2021.